

Spatial Analysis of National Football League (NFL) data

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Summary

Data available for the American National Football League (NFL) presents many opportunities for spatial analysis. Is team location influential on the performance of that team? Our paper provides a brief overview of our spatial analysis of the historical results data for all NFL teams. In our analysis we found that team location alone is not a strong predictor of team performance in NFL competition. Opportunities for further work including considering environmental and climatic factors at stadium locations, ground capacity, socio-economic conditions in the host city and so on.

KEYWORDS: spatial data, spatial analysis, football, NFL

1. Introduction

The National Football League (NFL) is the professional American football league in the United States of America with 32 teams divided into conferences and divisions. The NFL is subject to intensive statistical analysis by coaches, scouts, pundits, gamblers, investors and so on with existing literature outlining methods of predicting outcomes of games (Beal, Norman, & Ranchurn, 2020). For example, Borghesi (2007) considered performance of NFL teams and found that game day temperature significantly affects team performance. Most major cities in the United States of America have a home NFL team or franchise bringing a geographical aspect to how teams are arranged into divisions and the subsequent travel schedules of teams. Nichols (2012) found that there was a small, but difficult to quantify disadvantage for teams travelling west to east while Clay (2015) found a similar result for college basketball in the United States. We found that despite the influence of geographical location there appeared to be little documented research on how this geographical aspect of the NFL impacted on team performance. Literature related to NFL game outcomes are focused on the game predictions for the purposes of sports betting. The aim of this paper is to perform a preliminary investigation of some of the geospatial aspects of the game fixture schedules over the entire Superbowl era (since 1966) in the NFL. Our paper will provide some interesting initial results and encourage more in-depth research on the geospatial aspects of the NFL.

2. Data Acquisition

A dataset detailing every regular and post-season game of the SuperBowl era, that is from 1966 to 2020, was created via the use of the *rvest*³ package in R. R code was written to web-scrape game data from ProFootballReference⁴, a public database of NFL records and player statistics. Figure 1⁵ shows how the data was processed and cleaned to produce a well structured dataset. The original dataset lacked any references to location, aside from indicating if the winner/loser of the game played at home, away, or in a neutral location. A historical record of the various home stadium locations was used in order to join on the spatial coordinates for the location of each game. The final dataset is an

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³ <https://cloud.r-project.org/web/packages/rvest/index.html>

⁴ <https://www.pro-football-reference.com/>

⁵ <https://github.com/paddeaux/nfl-spatial-analysis>

ERSI Shapefile containing the results, statistics and locations of 12,993 games.

Figure 1 – NFL Data Acquisition Flowchart

The structure of the NFL consists of 32 teams spread across the United States. Figure 2 shows a map of the current configuration of NFL franchises and their locations as of 2020.

Figure 2 - Map of NFL Team Locations

3. Travel Distance & Team Performance

Up to the 2021 season, all teams host eight home games, and attend eight away games, totalling 16 regular season games across the season. The locations of certain teams result in some teams having much easier travel schedules than others. Table 1 below shows the highest season totals for travel distance, per season for each team. We create a metric called home-away-home (HAH) distance which indicates the sum of the distance required to travel to and then return home from an away game. This is calculated using the *st_distance* function present in the R package *sf*, which calculates the straight-line distance between the home and away team locations for a given game. Twice this distance is given as the *HAH* distance, as it represents the round-trip distance for a team to travel from home to an away game, and back again. Table 1 shows that teams in the West Coast routinely travel much greater distances, both on a weekly basis and for the season as a whole, with California-based teams regularly traveling twice that of the league average for the year.

Table 1 – Top 10 Teams by Total Home-Away-Home Distance

Year	Team	Total Wins	Total Losses	Total HAH Distance (km)	Average Weekly HAH Distance (km)	League Mean Total HAH Distance (km)
2013	San Francisco 49ers	14	5	70,672	3,720	27,207
2018	Los Angeles Chargers	13	5	65,331	3,630	
1998	San Francisco 49ers	13	5	62,722	3,485	26,934
1986	San Francisco 49ers	10	6	60,892	3,582	28,355
2008	Los Angeles Chargers	9	9	60,629	3,368	27,979
2012	Seattle Seahawks	12	16	60,426	3,357	27,333
1983	Los Angeles Rams	10	8	60,300	3,350	28,729
1989	Los Angeles Rams	13	6	58,991	3,105	29,542
1980	Las Vegas Raiders	15	5	58,776	2,939	29,030
1996	San Francisco 49ers	18	1	58,229	3,235	27,045

3.1 Travel Distance and Win/Loss Record

Can a difficult travel schedule affect a team's performance? A general means of determining a relationship between a team's win-loss record and the total distance travelled is visualized in Figure 3. The Win/Loss differential is the value of the number of losses subtracted from the number of wins in one season. There are no ties in NFL games. It is clear from this plot, and a correlation value of just 0.148, that there does not appear to be a relationship between total distance travelled per season and win/loss record. The San Francisco 49ers, who routinely travel immense distances every season due to their location, remain one of the more successful franchises in the NFL.

Figure 3 – Win/Loss Differential vs. Season Home-Away-Home Distance

3.2 Travel Distance and Week to Week Performance

Considering the patterns of points against and points for combined with the weekly distance travelled may give an indication of long travel distance affecting performance week-to-week. The distance metric used here is the *home-away (HA)* distance, as on a per-game basis, the return distance a team must travel after playing a game would not factor. By using the difference in *points for* and *points against* for a team we can easily see if a team won, indicated by a positive points difference, or lost, indicated by a negative points difference. Figure 4 shows a plot of points difference against the HA distance travelled by the same team. The plot shows little indication that distance travelled to a game affects the points differential of a team in any meaningful way.

Figure 4 – Points Differential vs. Home-Away Distance

Another metric which may indicate influence performance is the *yards gained* and *yards allowed (conceded)* metric. We found a weak correlation between the mean yards gained per game and the number of wins a team has in a season. This same result applies to the number of yards allowed (conceded) and eventual game losses. Figure 5 shows a similar distribution of points, indicating that there is no strong relationship between distance traveled to games and the subsequent game performance in terms of yards gained and yards allowed.

Figure 5 – Yards Differential vs. Home-Away Distance

3. Summary & Future Work

The aim of this paper was to perform a preliminary investigation of some of the geospatial aspects of the game fixture schedules over the entire Superbowl era. We created our own spatial dataset containing details of over 12,000 games. From the results presented in this paper, there appears to be little evidence to support the suggestion that a difficult travel schedule, at least in terms of kilometres travelled, has an effect on a teams performance. The data shows that successful teams, like the San Francisco 49ers can often travel a great deal more on average than less successful teams like the Detroit Lions, and vice versa. We did not find any strong relationship between the distance travelled by teams and their ability to score points, gain yards or their conceding of yards. At this point more detailed research is needed to assess the effects of other spatial aspects on team/player performance.

4. References

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Biographies

Paddy Gorry is currently completing his taught MSc of Data Science & Analytics at Maynooth University. He hopes to enrol in a Data Science-based PhD programme in the near future. Paddy is interested in using visualisation and spatial analysis for data science projects. This is his first academic paper.

Peter Mooney is a lecturer in the Department of Computer Science at Maynooth University. His main research interests are linked to computational approaches to the analysis of spatial data. He is currently a member of the GISRUK National Steering Committee.